

HIGH TEMPERATURE HYBRID COMPOSITES FOR THERMAL BARRIER APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In order to improve the thermal properties of a polymeric matrix, hollow glass microspheres (HGM) and carbon nanotubes-hollow glass microspheres hybrids (CNT-HGM) were added. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and infrared thermal imaging were performed. Dynamic mechanical analysis shows an improvement of 50% in storage modulus for 10 wt.% CNT-HGM composites. In this work it has been demonstrated how to produce material with good thermal insulating behaviour while maintaining acceptable mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) can meet multiple-functional requirements at prolonged service temperature. However, new aerospace vehicles have pushed sustained service temperatures into higher temperature ranges well beyond the capabilities of traditional CFRPs. When composite structures, such that located near engines in aircraft, are heated to temperatures greater than composite glass transition temperature, weight loss, chemical reactions and mechanical properties losses due to thermal aging occurs.

In this work, we have developed a material able to withstand high temperatures and, at the same time, able to act as a thermal insulator to protect other sensitive structures. Our approach is based on the dispersion of hollow microspheres in a high-temperature resin in order to obtain a composite with a high air volume-fraction, providing a polymeric material with low thermal conductivity and low density.

This approach has already been investigated, producing both thermoplastic and thermoset matrix composites [1–3]. Composites with a reduced thermal conductivity, light weight and improved specific mechanical properties have been produced [4,5].

We also propose the addition of a hybrid microstructure composed by CNT grown on the surface of the HGM, with the aim to improve the adhesion of the microspheres to the matrix [7,8] and consequently improve the mechanical properties of the produced composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The resin used in this work for the preparation of the composites was an urethane acrylate resin (Crestapol 1234, density 1.04 kg/m³). For curing at room temperature the resin requires the addition of a catalyst and an accelerator. Methyl-ethyl-ketone peroxide solution in diisobutyl phthalate (Butanox LPT) was used as catalyst and cobalt octoate dissolved in styrene was used as accelerator.

Hollow glass microspheres (3M) were used as filler for the composites. These microspheres have a particle size distribution between 20 and 105 μm ; the density is 0.2 kg/m^3 and the thermal conductivity at 21 $^\circ\text{C}$ is 0.07 W/mK . The CNT-HGM hybrid material is synthesized using the hollow microspheres as source material following the method described in the next section.

2.2 Hybrid structures synthesis and composites preparation

Hybrid structures were synthesized by directly growing CNT on the surface of the hollow glass microspheres, using a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process previously described [9]. The catalyst precursor for the CNT growth used in this work was iron nitrate. In order to coat the surface with the catalyst precursor, the microspheres were added to a solution of iron nitrate in isopropanol and mixed. Then, the mixture was filtered for overnight and dried at 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours.

Composites containing 0, 2, 5 and 10 wt.% of HGM and composites containing 0, 2, 5 and 10 wt.% of CNT-HGM were produced. All composites were prepared according to the following steps: (1) resin, catalyst and accelerator were mixed and degassed for 10 minutes; (2) the appropriate amount of filler is added to the resin and stirred by hand; (3) the resulting mixtures are poured in moulds and cured at room temperature for 48 hours, followed by a post-cure cycle of 5 hours at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ and then 3 hours at 200 $^\circ\text{C}$.

2.3 Characterization

The as-received microspheres and microspheres after the CVD process were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (EVO MA15, Carl Zeiss). The samples were sputter coated with a thin layer of gold prior SEM characterization.

Thermal stability and carbon content of the CNT-microspheres was analyzed using a thermogravimetric analyzer (Q50, TA Instruments) in a temperature range from room temperature to 800 $^\circ\text{C}$, with a heating rate of 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in oxygen environment.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed on a Q800 (TA Instruments) testing specimens with dimensions of 11x 30x 3 mm, in the temperature range between room temperature and 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ at a frequency of 1 Hz and a heating rate of 3 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

The thermal behavior of the composites with 10 wt.% HGM and CNT-HGM was qualitatively analyzed using an infrared camera (FLIR). Cylindrical samples, with a diameter of 30 mm and a thickness of 3 mm, were placed on a heating plate that was heated up to 150 $^\circ\text{C}$. Once that temperature is reached, the samples were taken from the heating plate and immediately placed on a teflon plate at room temperature. Images were taken during the cooling-down process.

3. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The SEM images show that the as-received HGM have a size distribution between 20 and 100 μm , approximately. It can be observed that the microspheres are well dispersed, with no observable agglomerates, and that just a few of them are broken (Figure 1 a). After being held at 600 $^\circ\text{C}$ during the CVD process, the hollow microspheres maintain their spherical shape. This seems to indicate that no melting process had taken place (Figure 1 b). In this image can also be seen that the CNT grown by the CVD process cover the surface of HGM, although not completely.

Figure 1. SEM images of (a) the as-received microspheres, (b) the CNT-microspheres (microspheres after the CVD process). It can be observed in (a) that as-received hollow glass microspheres are not agglomerated. The insert in (b) shows CNT, which are grown on the surface of the microspheres and partially covers it.

The thermogravimetric analysis shows that the glass microspheres are thermally stable up to 800 °C. After the CVD process, the microspheres have an increase of 33 wt.% what is mainly due to the CNTs. By this analysis is also determined that the obtained CNTs have an oxidation temperature of 570 °C.

The storage modulus was obtained from the dynamic mechanical analysis [10]. The composites with CNT-HGM hybrid structures possess higher storage modulus than the HGM composites and the neat resin (Figure 2). At high temperature (300 °C), the storage modulus remains approximately constant with the addition of HGM but the storage modulus increases 50% for the 10 wt.% CNT-HGM composite. This improvement could be explained by the addition of CNT-microspheres to the matrix. After the mixing process, during the preparation of the composites, the CNT remain located around the HGM. The presence of CNT located on the surface of microspheres seems to promote a better microsphere/matrix interface in comparison with the apparently weak interface of the HGM composites, what could be proved by the clean debonding holes observed.

The qualitative analysis of the thermal behaviour of the composites is performed by infrared thermography (Figure 3). In the first infrared image obtained when the samples were taken from the heating plate ($t=0$ min), the neat resin is at highest temperature (126 °C), while CNT-HGM and HGM composites had reached only 121 and 119 °C, respectively. One minute later, the 10 wt.% of CNT-HGM sample is at 69 °C, while the HGM composite and neat resin are at higher temperature (71 and 81 °C, respectively). At the end of the cooling-down process, the CNT-HGM composite has reached the room temperature (23 °C), while the HGM composite and the neat resin are 1 and 3 °C above the room temperature.

It can be concluded that the addition of HGM composites reduce the heat transmitted compared with the neat resin. This could be explained because of the low thermal conductivity of the HGM. The presence of CNT, which have a high thermal conductivity, on the surface of the HGM seems to slightly increase the transmission of heat [11], compared with the HGM composite.

Figure 2. Storage modulus vs. composites filler wt.% content, measured at room temperature and at 300 °C. For room temperature the CNT-HGM composites have a higher storage modulus than the HGM composites and neat resin.

Figure 3. Cooling process of samples of resin, HGM composites and CNT-HGM composites observed with an infrared camera. It seems that CNT grown on the surface of the HGM increases the rate of heat evacuation, compared with the HGM composites. Nonetheless, the pure resin seems to have the lower rate of heat evacuation

Further research will be focused on the quantitative measurement of the thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity in order to validate the qualitative characterization done with the infrared camera. Differential scanning calorimetry will be used to measure the glass transition temperature of both types of composites produced with HGM and the hybrid CNT-HGM. This will help identify any possible changes compared to neat resin. The addition of CNT on the surface of the HGM modifies the electrical behavior of the composites, thus it is necessary to characterize the electrical conductivity of the CNT-HGM composites.

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